

Robust Detection of Heart Beats in Multimodal Data

Operations Research Project

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Abstract

This paper focuses on different algorithms for robust QRS detection using the ECG signals of human patients. Methods that are discussed in this report include Hilbert transformation, Wavelet-based approach and Pan-Tompkins algorithm. Additionally, a novel hybrid method combining above mentioned techniques is introduced. The performance of the algorithms was tested using ECG waveform records from the training set provided for Computing in Cardiology challenge of 2014. Hilbert transformation managed to outperform other techniques, including the hybrid approach, with a sensitivity of 99.94 and predictivity of 99.91 in the training set. Moreover, possible enhancement is discussed through the use of different channels, however further general improvement was not achieved.

1 Introduction

In the field of medicine, in order to perform highly complex surgical interventions successfully, properties of the human body have to be surveilled at all times. Some important characteristics are the heart beat, the blood pressure and the respiration. The **electrocardiogram** or **ECG**, which monitors the heart beat, has the highest significance as it is one of the most important elements in the doctors' decisions for the regulation of medication or life-saving measures. If incorrect decisions are made here, it may cost the patient's life. However, the **ECG** can sometimes be obfuscated to such a degree that the heart beats can no longer be identified precisely. In order to maintain precise heart beat detection, specially designed algorithms can overcome distortions in the heart's signal, taking into account previously gathered data or other signals if necessary. This paper will describe such an algorithm.

The detection of heart beats is an internationally accepted problem, featured on the **PhysioNet** website as a competition for developing accurate software ([9]). Alluding to this competition, **Maastricht University** has launched a semester project aiming at the same goal. The knowledge gained from the **Operations Research** programme courses should be used to develop an algorithm for accurate heart beat detection among different groups of students, with each algorithm competing against each other in a final competition.

The goal of this paper is to describe the noise-resistant analysis of the above mentioned signals in order to precisely detect the heart beats. To achieve this, different algorithms for the analysis are presented and their benefits and disadvantages are compared by using them on datasets from different origins and measuring their performance.

Section 2 briefly describes the theory behind the **ECG** signals, as well as measures to improve quality control throughout development and implementation. In section 3, the different algorithms and their combinations are explained in detail. After that, section 4 elaborates on experiments made to improve the results gained in section 3, such as applying artificial noise to the signals. Finally, the results for the available datasets are presented, compared and commented on in section 5, and a conclusion is given in section 6.

2 Background

Before going into detail about each algorithm, some basic knowledge is necessary. Therefore, a brief description about **ECG** signals is given in section 2.1. Additionally, section 2.2 describes actions that were taken to easily analyse and visualise results in order to be able to work more efficiently and more effective with the algorithms.

2.1 ECG signals

In order to use **ECG** signals to detect heart beats, the structure of those signals should be analysed. The **ECG** signal captures the electrical activity of the heart muscle, measured with electrodes applied to the skin. The measured voltage has a magnitude of 1 mV, which makes accurate equipment necessary because this signal is very prone to noise.

The **ECG** signal contains a recurring pattern which is very distinctive for this signal. It contains five deflections that are called **P**-waves, **QRS** complexes and **T**-waves. The **T**-wave relates to the *depolarisation of the atria*, the **QRS** complex is caused by the *ventricular depolarisation* and the **T**-wave originates in the *ventricular repolarisation* ([4]). An example of such a **QRS** complex is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Example of a **ECG** signal with highlighted parts

The **QRS** complex from Figure 1 has a very prominent shape, which is the reason why heart beat detectors use **R**-wave detection to extrapolate the heart beat from the **ECG** signal ([4]).

2.2 Visualisation and quality control

In the early stages of algorithm development, decent debugging possibilities are very important. While tuning the different approaches, it is important to see where errors occur or where the methods diverge from annotations. For evaluating further steps, it is also helpful to see the signals in their entirety (or at least in a way that inferences can be made about the connection of the signals), for example when discussing the importance of other signals with regard to the **ECG** or trends in the distances of the **ECG** peaks.

The *PhysioNet* website hosts a visualisation service named **LightWave** ([5]) that can plot all channels and annotated pulses for each of the given test datasets in one large graph, allowing for a good analysis for the channels' interconnections. However, given by the compact display, the signals will overlap if there is a certain amount of noise in the data, which can make it difficult to work with. Moreover, the tool can only display a very limited amount of datasets, so externally acquired or customly produced datasets cannot be viewed at all. Additionally, *Matlab* offers various possibilities of displaying the channels, but those do not offer the well-arranged display of all signals. To improve workability, an alternative way of displaying had to be developed.

To enable the group to evaluate results without suffering from the above mentioned drawbacks, a new program was developed, making use of the **C#** programming language. The first version only aimed at displaying all channels for visual analysis, but as the group proceeded with their work, new features were gradually implemented.

Figure 2: Software displaying the channels of a dataset

The software lets the user navigate through the signals by means of two scroll bars. Errors can be easily spotted as each annotated pulse is highlighted by a green or red area in case of a success (the pulse was accurately determined) or a failure (the pulse is missing or the distance exceeds 150 milliseconds). For the quick comparison of the algorithms, the software reads all available datasets and computes a quality value for each algorithm. In order to make the algorithms resistant to noise, the channels can be provided with a variety of noise; the algorithms can be tweaked in performance afterwards. This noise generation will be described in detail in section 4.2.

As soon as the first algorithms were able to give results, a possibility was needed to evaluate those results in order to rank the algorithms. A method was introduced, comparing the identified pulses with the annotated pulses from *PhysioNet* and calculating a quality value from them.

The values shown on the right hand side of Figure 2 were gained using the evaluation function which will be presented in detail in section 4.1, the results follow in section 5.

3 Signal processing

In order to be able to determine the pulses, the data must first be processed in some way. Due to the fact that the **ECG** peaks are sometimes not detectable because they are obscured or missing, specially designed algorithms process the signal in such a way that the peaks can be registered by a simple peak detection algorithm afterwards.

The following algorithms all work identically to a certain extent, according to Figure 3. Sections 3.1 through 3.4 will cover the preprocessing stage. Section 3.5 will cover the decision stage.

Figure 3: Common structure of **QRS** detection by signal processing ([3])

3.1 Pan-Tompkins

The *Pan-Tompkins* algorithm does not require expert knowledge and can easily be implemented ([8]). It is based on the analysis of the slope, amplitude and width of the **QRS** complexes. Figure 4 shows the different steps of the algorithm: A band-pass filter that takes the derivative of the signal and squares it, a moving-average filter for integration of the signal and a search procedure.

Figure 4: Steps in the *Pan-Tompkins* algorithm ([6])

The **band-pass filter** is used to reduce the influence of noise on the signal. In order for the pass band to maximise the **QRS** energy and suppress all other energy, cut-off frequencies of magnitude 5 - 30 [Hz] are used.

The second stage is the **differentiation** of the signal. This operation will emphasise parts of the signal with a steep slope. Therefore, the steep peak of the **QRS** complexes will be emphasised, while the gradual slopes of the **P**- and **T**-waves will be suppressed.

By **squaring** the signal, those parts that were already emphasised will be enlarged even further. Additionally, the negative parts of the **QRS**'s downward slope are turned positive.

The **integration** of the signal is realised by a moving average filter. This will combine peaks closer to each other, such as the up and down slopes of the **QRS** complex. Furthermore, small noisy peaks will be smoothed. The width of such a search window should be chosen such that it is wide enough to include the duration of abnormal extended **QRS** complexes, but short enough that it does not include both an **R**- and a **T**-wave. The width results in a trade-off between false detections (false positives) and missed detections (false negatives).

3.2 Hilbert transformation

The Hilbert transformation (**HT**) is an alternative to the *Pan-Tompkins* algorithm for discrete data. It works similar to convolution, with the difference of using differentiation instead of windowing (as in short term Fourier transformation, **STFT**), which attempts to solve the *time-frequency indeterminacy*.

With the **HT**, the derivative of the phase (provided by the polar representation of the analytic signal) with respect to time yields instantaneous frequencies that are functions of time, so the result actually is an *energy distribution over time and frequency*.

While the **STFT** only says that some frequency persisted in the data, the **HT** gives the likelihood for that frequency at a given time. The signal can consist of multiple instantaneous frequencies, so it should be cleaned first. Therefore, a bandpass filter of 9 - 30 [Hz] is used. This combination represents the preprocessing stage from Figure 3.

The **HT** defines the imaginary part of the function to make it an analytic function, i.e. a function whose signal strength is zero for all frequency components less than zero. This is shown in equation 1.

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_a(t) &= \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{X(f) + X(f) \cdot \text{sign}(f)\} \\
 &= \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{X(f)\} + \underbrace{\mathcal{F}^{-1}\{X(f)\} \cdot \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\text{sign}(f)\}}_{\text{convolution}} \\
 &= x(t) + j \underbrace{\left[x(t) \cdot \frac{1}{\pi t} \right]}_{\hat{x}(t)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

In order to find **ECG** peaks in the analytical signal, an envelope of the signal is created that is composed of only real values, as shown in equation 2. After this pre-processing, any method can now be used to find peaks (cf. decision stage in Figure 3). Detected peaks will be shifted a few milliseconds due to the transformation, which is negligible.

$$B(t) = \sqrt{x(t)^2 + X(t)^2} \tag{2}$$

3.3 Wavelet transformation

The wavelet transformation is a linear operation that decomposes the signal into a number of scales related to frequency components, which are then scaled with a certain resolution. As many other pre-processing techniques, the signal should be normalised and/or be cleaned of noise before passing it to other techniques, i.e. *Pan-Tompkins* or *Hilbert transformation*. Image below shows the steps of wavelet decomposition. Detail and approximation coefficients are computed by applying low-pass and high-pass filters on the signal. For this research paper, daubechy-2 wavelets have been used. Next to adjusting coefficients, which will be discussed later in the section, wavelet-based approach also tries to remove some other noise artifacts.

Two dominant types of artifacts found in **ECGs** are:

- High-frequency noise cause by electromyogram interference, power line interference or mechanical forces acting on the electrodes
- Baseline drift (**BD**) that may occur due to respiration, the motion of the patients or the instruments removal

One known approach of removing the **BD** is:

- Apply 200ms median filter to remove **P**-waves
- Apply 600ms median filter to remove **T**-waves
- Subtract the resulting signal from the original signal

This way, the result (which is only the **BD**) can be removed from the original signal, as shown in Figure 5.

Next, the actual *wavelet transformation* attempts to get rid of the noise. Therefore, the signal is decomposed and detail coefficients of the decomposition pass through thresholding. The method applied is *soft thresholding* with a constant value which corresponds to the *universal threshold*, given by the formula $\sqrt{2 \cdot \log(\text{length}_{\text{signal}})}$ ([2]). After that, the signal is reconstructed through inverse wavelet transformation and sent to one of the techniques described in the previous sections.

Figure 5: Removing **BD** from an **ECG** signal

3.4 Combination of algorithms

After developing the three separate algorithms mentioned above, they were merged in order to combine each algorithm's strengths and even out their weaknesses. The combined algorithm works as follows, as shown in Figure 6.

- Preprocessing: Wavelet filtering (Daubechies 2 wavelet)
- Signal processing: *Hilbert* (primary) or *Pan-Tompkins* (secondary)
- Decision making: Adaptive thresholding, as explained in section 3.5

Figure 6: Five stages of the algorithm

3.5 Decision making

After the signal processing, the signal must be thresholded in order to identify the peaks, which is the decision making part of Figure 3. A peak is said to be a local maximum with no higher points in a certain interval around it. There are three different thresholding techniques:

By using a **fixed treshold**, one threshold value is set for all patients. One possibility for this is the mean of the current signal. This technique is very prone to differences in the individual signals.

The use of a **naïve adaptive threshold** ([4]) gets rid of that problem:

- 1) Set an initial threshold slightly lower than the maximum of the signal
 $(v_{threshold} = 0.95 \cdot v_{max})$

- 2) Set a stepsize ($v_{step} = 0.03 \cdot v_{max}$)
- 3) Determine the peaks in the signal above the threshold, identify number of peaks
- 4) Decrease threshold by stepsize ($v_{threshold} = v_{threshold} - v_{step}$)
- 5) Redo from 3) until in one step, no new peaks are found

However, the above approach is prone to changes *inside* the signal. This might be solved by using a proper **adaptive thresholding** technique ([8]) that updates the threshold online during the analysis of the signal. It uses the first two seconds to set an initial value for the threshold and then for each peak proceeds as shown in Figure 7. The peaks verified by the method are added to the result set.

Figure 7: Adaptive thresholding steps

Another aspect that has to be taken into account is the presence of multiple **ECG** signals among which the best signal must be chosen. It is known that *atrial fibrillation* is characterised by a dominant frequency in the range of 3-12 [Hz] ([1]).

If a dataset has multiple **ECG** signals, the Fourier spectrum of each is calculated. The signal with the highest energy within the range of 3 and 12 [Hz] will be chosen as the best and most reliable signal. The result is shown in Figure 8.

3.6 Using other channels

It is possible to encounter situations similar to Figure 9. Due to missing information in the most important channel, the algorithm has nothing to work with, so all pulses in that particular area will be missed and in the worst case, the threshold may be decreased and

Figure 8: Example of the adaptive threshold

many false positives will follow as soon as the **ECG** returns.

Figure 9: A missing **ECG** signal is impossible to work with for conventional algorithms

This can be averted by having a contingency plan for this case: Discard the useless parts of the **ECG** signal and move on to another one. However, not all the signals are suitable for

this strategy:

- **EEG**, **EMG** and **EOG** are measurements of electrical activity originating from different muscles. As there is no straightforward way of analysing them, those channels were deemed to be not useful in this case.
- The respiration volumes of chest or abdomen can increase or decrease throughout many heart beats, but do not contain any traces of those.
- The **O₂**-saturation of the blood is connected with the muscle movement and the respiration, i.e. two channels that were already discarded. Additionally, the changes are far too slow to be helpful for precise measurements.
- The blood pressure (**BP**) increases shortly after every heart beat and decreases until the next beat. This channel is strongly connected to the **ECG** and will be used below.

When taking a look at the **BP**, the first thing to be noted is the offset between any heart beat and the following peak in the **BP**: This value seems to be constant within a small interval. To make the calculations easier, it was assumed to be **constant for each patient**, although the offset should scale with the blood pressure to a certain extent. Thus, the task at hand is to find the peaks in the **BP**, determine the delay to the **ECG** and to know when to switch to this algorithm.

The algorithm to process **BP** signal is quite similar to the one from the **ECG** analysis:

Figure 10: Steps for **BP** analysis

In Figure 11, the difference of blood pressure peaks and **ECG** peaks is shown, along with a delay between them.

In most cases, the estimated **BP** pulse totally coincides with the **ECG** pulse. As both the **ECG** signal and the **BP** signal can be subject to noise, no single signal can be seen as definitive. The combination tries to detect false positives and false negatives in the **ECG** signal based on the **BP**. To detect false positives all peaks in the **ECG** signal are checked for corresponding **BP** peaks. An **ECG** peak with no corresponding **BP** peak is a false positive if there are corresponding **BP** peaks for the previous and the next **ECG** peaks and the peak is not within the mean distance of the last 5 peaks. Otherwise no definitive choice can be made on the **BP** signal and the peak is kept as regular.

After false positives are removed false negatives need to be checked. This can only be done in this order because false positives would hide missing peaks otherwise.

To detect false negatives all peaks in the **BP** signal are checked for corresponding **ECG** peaks. A false negative is identified if there is no corresponding **ECG** peak for a given **BP**

Figure 11: Data from the **BP** transferred to the **ECG**: The **red** circles show the detected pulses in the **BP** channel. The **magenta** crosses show the estimated peak location after subtracting the offset. Finally, the **green** circles show the peaks in the **ECG** signal.

peak and the distance between the last and the next **ECG** peak is bigger than $1.66 \cdot \text{mean}$ while the distance between the **BP** peak and the surrounding **BP** peaks is bigger than $0.3 \cdot \text{mean}$ distance. A **BP** peak without a corresponding **ECG** peak that violates one of the distance constraints is ignored.

4 Experiments

Section 3 gave a detailed description of the different algorithm modules and the development of a *hybrid* algorithm. This section will describe experimental setups used for the assessment of the algorithms. This includes the interpretation of the results, evaluation of the robustness or manipulation of certain parameters.

4.1 Assessment of methods

In order to evaluate our algorithms and to examine the output, the tool presented in section 2 was used. This tool uses the evaluation function stated in equations 3 and 4. This tool reads all databases from a specific location and provides the outputs of the algorithms.

$$\mathbf{SE} = \frac{\mathbf{TP}}{\mathbf{TP} + \mathbf{FN}} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{PP} = \frac{\mathbf{TP}}{\mathbf{TP} + \mathbf{FP}} \quad (4)$$

with true positives (**TP**) being the number of correctly identified pulses, false negatives (**FN**) the number of missed annotated pulses and false positives (**FP**) the number of incorrectly identified non-existing pulses. These values will count equally in the final evaluation; however, they have to be interpreted quite differently: The sensitivity is used to determine the chance of missing pulses, whereas the predictivity stands for the reliability that an identified pulse exists.

The values mentioned above are then calculated for every available database and the mean and standard deviation are calculated. As mentioned in section 2.2, this evaluation is also used in the self-written software to quickly determine whether a change in the code led to an improvement or a deterioration of the results.

4.2 Verification of robustness

An important part of the challenge is making sure the method developed is robust. Because the fraction of the provided data that is distorted by noise is unknown, the realistic precision could not be estimated. For example, assuming the algorithm finds all peaks that are not noisy and the percentage of noisy pulses is 1%, a precision of 99% would be equivalent to having missed all of those.

An approach taken in order to overcome this uncertainty involved testing the algorithms on very noisy datasets and tweaking their parameters in order to cope with this overall noise. This would increase the chance to also capture the noisy pulses in an otherwise clean

signal. Therefore, artificial noise was applied to the available signals in order to increase the overall performance. The following change in performance would indicate how resistant the algorithms are to noise.

Usually, measured signals are assumed to be corrupted with white Gaussian noise with mean 0 and some unknown variance. This kind of noise can easily be added to a signal, but it is also very easy to remove. In fact, many algorithms have an implicit noise reduction implemented, so in order to improve the quality and robustness, they need to be confronted with different types of noise.

White Gaussian noise corrupts all frequencies with the same power. However, adding noise having different amplitudes of power over frequency spectrum will lead to better assessment of robustness. Coloured noise ([7]) is a state-of-the-art approach of introducing noise where amplitude of power varies over frequency spectrum.

Pink or *brown* noise is a type of noise where the power decreases with increasing frequency ($\frac{1}{f}$ -noise), depending on the level of decrease. *Blue* or *violet* noise is noise where the power increases with the frequency (f -noise), depending on the level of increase. Furthermore, *gray* noise is a psychoacoustic combination of f -noise and $\frac{1}{f}$ -noise. Figure 12 shows the proportion of intensity and frequency for each type in more detail.

Figure 12: Frequency spectrum for different types of noise

Figure 13 and Figure 14 show a signal corrupted with different types of noise, with the original pulses indicated by red arrows.

Figure 13: An originally noise-free signal, corrupted with low-frequency *brown* noise. Obviously, this type of noise can easily obscure or even invert pulses or provoke false positives

Figure 14: An originally noise-free signal, corrupted with high-frequency *violet* noise. The pulses are still recognisable, but false positives can occur here as well due to high local spikes

The noise was applied in the following way: First, all six types of noise were applied on the entire signal, yielding six corrupted signals. Next, sections of a fixed size were arbitrarily chosen from those signals. Finally, these sections were combined to get a signal that is composed of many different types of noise. Seeing how the algorithms reacts to that noise and tweaking the parameters accordingly, they should perform better against natural noise.

In addition to artificial noise, the attempt was made to obtain other databases from *PhysioNet*, ideally with noise, for our algorithms to test. While the website holds a large amount of those, most of them could not be used, mainly due to the following reasons:

- Most datasets did not have any annotated pulses
- Annotated pulses often covered two different **ECG** signals
- Some datasets were just base lines (same value everywhere)
- **QRS** complexes have odd shapes the algorithms cannot deal with

There was one collection of datasets without the above flaws. It contained some **ECG** signals with strong peaks and some very noisy datasets (namely `test_set_a`). Those 30 datasets were added to the test sets and its evaluation should let us improve the parameters of the final algorithm.

4.3 Optimisation of parameters

Each algorithm has several parameters that influence its effectivity. The attempt was made to identify the best parameter setting in order to achieve the highest results. If many parameters can be changed, the number of settings that can be tested and evaluated quickly increases, so a good optimisation algorithm is needed, such as *simulated annealing*. However, only two parameters were found with a high impact on the results, so they were evaluated manually (by brute force).

In the case of *Hilbert* and *Pan-Tompkins*, the cut-off frequencies of the band-pass filter were the only parameters of interest. No consensus about exact frequencies could be found in the literature, so different settings were tried according to the range of frequencies specified there. The lower cut-off frequency was tested in the range of 2 - 10 [Hz], the upper one between 25 and 45 [Hz] (see [3], [6] and [8]).

In the case of the combined algorithm, the only parameter of interest was the minimum time between peaks in the peak finding algorithm. This states that there cannot be two peaks with a time difference lower than that value. If multiple peaks are found in this range, the highest one is chosen.

5 Results

This section describes the different results obtained throughout the development process, as well as comment on the choices made when deciding for or against certain algorithms.

In the beginning, the algorithms were run on the 100 provided datasets. Table 1 recaps the performance of different algorithms. Results demonstrate that Hilbert transformation outperforms the other techniques, including the hybrid approach. Furthermore, hybrid did not perform better than other two approaches as well, suggesting the poor combination of algorithms. Reason behind it might be the contrast between the processing steps and the assumptions of the different approaches.

Table 1: Performance of algorithms on clean dataset, depicting *mean \pm standard deviation*

Algorithm	Sensitivity	Predictivity
PT	99.93% \pm 0.19%	99.56% \pm 0.99%
H	99.91% \pm 0.26%	99.92% \pm 0.24%
W	99.71% \pm 0.45%	99.82% \pm 0.41%
Hybrid + PT	98.86% \pm 6.82%	99.84% \pm 0.43%
Hybrid + H	98.84% \pm 9.98%	99.72% \pm 1.47%

Results shown in Table 1 suggest the high accuracy for algorithms. However, as mentioned in Section 4.2, this might be due to the lack of noise in the training set. In order to verify and further assess the robustness and quality of techniques, noise-corrupted dataset is used for experiments. Table 2 shows the outcome of this experiment. One positive result that can be extracted from Table 2 concerns the robustness of methods. As it can be seen, performance did not decrease drastically, implying that techniques can deal with datasets having different types of noise.

Table 2: Performance of algorithms on noisy dataset, depicting *mean \pm standard deviation*

Algorithm	Sensitivity	Predictivity
PT	98.91% \pm 2.31%	96.05% \pm 8.75%
H	98.68% \pm 3.18%	97.56% \pm 5.91%
W	97.70% \pm 4.64%	94.34% \pm 8.86%
Hybrid + PT	96.97% \pm 5.95%	95.67% \pm 8.50%
Hybrid + H	98.01% \pm 4.14%	96.88% \pm 6.97%

First two tables suggested that Hilbert-based algorithms will perform better. For that reason, optimisation experiments were performed on hybrid approach and Hilbert transformation Percentages obtained from the experiment are summarised in Table 3. Optimisation

improved the overall performance of the methods, making them more powerful and more accurate.

Table 3: Performance of algorithm on clean data after optimisation, depicting *mean \pm standard deviation*

Algorithm	Sensitivity	Predictivity
H	99.92% \pm 0.24%	99.94% \pm 0.15%
Hybrid + H	99.81% \pm 0.48%	99.97% \pm 0.58%
Hybrid + PT	99.73% \pm 0.69%	99.72% \pm 0.58%

As it was the case with first experiment, next step is to analyse the robustness of the techniques with optimised parameters. Outcomes from the experiment can be seen on Table 4. As expected, percentages for different techniques have improved. Especially the hybrid approach, which had a low predictivity on noise-corrupted data seem to perform better after boosting.

Table 4: Performance of algorithm on noisy data after optimisation, depicting *mean \pm standard deviation*

Algorithm	Sensitivity	Predictivity
H	98.83% \pm 2.98%	97.33% \pm 6.98%
Hybrid + H	97.51% \pm 5.05%	96.33% \pm 7.29%
Hybrid + PT	96.86% \pm 6.35%	95.97% \pm 8.04%

All algorithms show improvement when combined with the BP signal (Table 5 and 6). Especially the Hilbert algorithm achieved almost perfect results. This leads to that combination being the prime algorithm to use on the final Data.

Table 5: Performance of algorithm on clean data using Blood Pressure, depicting *mean \pm standard deviation*

Algorithm	Sensitivity	Predictivity
H	99.99% \pm 0.05%	99.99% \pm 0.05%
Hybrid + H	99.96% \pm 0.15%	99.91% \pm 0.16%
Hybrid + PT	99.92% \pm 0.22%	99.91% \pm 0.23%

Hilbert transformation showed a better performance during the experiments, making it an appropriate choice for use on test set. Table 7 shows the results for the final test set of the competition. The outcome of this set is lower than results in the previous experiments. This is due to the fact that in 21 cases out of the 41 in the set, multiple ECG leads were present. The algorithm chose autonomous for the ECG lead with the most energy between 3 and 12 [Hz]. However, this resulted in 4 cases where the sensitivity and/or predictivity

Table 6: Performance of algorithm on noisy data using Blood Pressure, depicting *mean ± standard deviation*

Algorithm	Sensitivity	Predictivity
H	98.97% ± 7.12%	98.35% ± 8.15%
Hybrid + H	98.10% ± 9.90%	97.81% ± 10.12%
Hybrid + PT	98.40% ± 4.82%	98.05% ± 8.38%

were extremely low. To test the influence of this part of the algorithm, the testdata was run again, but for each signal the ecg-lead was chosen that gave the best results. The results from this experiment are much better, and more in line with the previous results.

Table 7: Performance on final test set *mean ± standard deviation*

Algorithm	Sensitivity	Predictivity	Median Sensitivity	Median Predictivity
Autonomous, with BP	86.1690% ± 25.5540%	84.4757% ± 27.6428%	99.7006%	99.8624%
Autonomous, no BP	94.1914% ± 18.7534%	92.4132% ± 21.2374%	99.7517%	99.9751%
Manual, no BP	99.3306% ± 1.3328%	97.4656% ± 8.1734%	99.7703%	99.9767%

6 Conclusion

The main problem addressed in this paper was the development of a robust method to detect the heartbeat of an arbitrary patient. The task is based on the *PhysioNet* challenge ([9]) and was adopted by **Maastricht University** to create a semester project.

PhysioNet had provided a rich database where datasets could be found for the methods to test, as well as a visual aid for debugging purposes. The examiners provided an evaluation function to produce comparable results of different approaches.

Some improvements were made in order to tackle the problem. A tool was developed in **C#** that could display the datasets in a different way than *PhysioNet* as well as add artificial noise to them. The three initial algorithms *Pan-Tompkins*, *Hilbert* and *Wavelet transformation* were compared and combined in order to achieve a better result. The information of channels other than the **ECG** was included and the algorithms' parameters were optimised in order to improve the results.

The current best method is the *Hilbert* algorithm without the use of **BP**. It was originally anticipated that **BP** would improve the algorithm; however, taking into account different **BP** channels could not be implemented in time.

The results from the testdata show that there was a drop in performance, due to the wrong choice of which ecg lead to use. When the lead was chosen autonomously, the predictivity and sensitivity were only 94.19% and 92.41% respectively. However, when the best ecg-lead was chosen manually, the results rose to 99.33% and 97.47% respectively.

6.1 Prospect

The following aspects should be taken into account for future research:

- The usefulness of other channels apart from **ECG** and **BP** could be investigated, such as **EEG**.
- After optimisation, the algorithm could be adapted in order to work on live measurement data, enabling it to work with actual heart beat monitoring.
- The blood pressure analysis needs to be adapted in order to cope with multiple **BP** channels.
- When multiple ecg leads are available, a better decision making should be implemented for which lead to use. Another option could be to combine the different leads by means of principle component analysis or other techniques.

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